

**THE PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS OF HOME ECONOMICS AS
INTRODUCED BY UNIVERSAL BASIC EDUCATION (UBE) IN PRIMARY
SCHOOLS:**

**A case study of selected primary schools in Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo Local
Government Area of Ondo State**

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Abstract

The introduction of Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme is an attempt at providing the Nigerian populace with unrestricted, unlimited and free education. This study was carried out to examine the problems and prospects of Home Economics as introduced by UBE in Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo local government area of Ondo State. Ten (10) primary schools were randomly selected in the local government area. Relevant data was collected through the use of structured questionnaire containing thirty (30) items. Data collected was analyzed using frequencies and percentages. Results showed that 83% of the respondents declared that there were not enough teachers in the schools selected. 75% responded that there were not enough teachers with Home Economics as their area of specialization. None of the selected schools had Home Economics laboratory and equipment. It is recommended that Home Economics teachers should be adequate in quality and quantity.

Introduction

Nigeria has recognized that her educational system has deteriorated due to a number of reasons and has not made as much progress as she would have liked it to make in attaining her Education For All (EFA) goals (EFA 2000). In order to address this undesirable situation, she has embarked on a reform of the entire system in order to provide not only access but also to improve the quality and efficiency of education in the country.

As a beginning, the new democratic government of Nigeria made education one of its priorities. The then President (Olusegun Obasanjo) launched the Universal Basic Education (UBE) on 29th September 1999 in Sokoto, Sokoto State.

According to UBE Commission of 2007 "there are three components of the UBE programme and these are

- i. Early Childhood and Development Education (ECCDE).
- ii. 6 years primary education
- iii. 3 years JSS education”

The UBE programme took-off effectively with the signing of the UBE Act in April 2004. However, the implementation started in earnest in July 2005 with the appropriation of the UBE fund to the commission and subsequent disbursement to states.

The UBE is not a new educational policy. It is provided within the context of the 6-3-3-4 National policy on education. It is a reinforcement of the 6-3-3-4 policy on education.

UBE could not take-off immediately after its launch, as it did not have legal backing. Nonetheless many UBE related activities were carried out in the areas of social mobilization, infrastructural development, provision of instructional material etc.

The beneficiaries of the UBE programme are as follows:

- i. Children aged 3-5 years for ECCDE
- ii. Children aged 6-11+ years for junior education
- iii. Children aged 12-14+ years for Junior Secondary School (JSS) education.

According to the UBE Commission 2007 “the ECCDE is not compulsory, what is compulsory is 6 years of primary and 3 year of JSS education”. Parents are however strongly encouraged to register their children in ECCDE centres while government is expected to provide ECCDE centres.

The new area of emphasis in the new 9 years basic Education Curriculum are:

- i. Value reorientation
- ii. Basic science
- iii. Basic technology
- iv. Computer Science
- v. Teaching of Thinking
- vi. Home Economics
- vii. Agriculture
- viii. Business Studies and
- ix. Civic Education
- x. Moral Instructions
- xi. French

It is generally accepted that the purpose of education is to train a child mentally, physically and spiritually to enable him to be useful to the society. Human psychology shows that for these objectives to be realized, adequate foundation has to be laid right from the cradle.

Primary education is the bedrock of formal education. It is a system which every child is expected to pass through if he is to receive any form of formal education. At present there are many problems facing

the teaching of Home Economics in Primary Schools as being introduced by the UBE.

Halidu (2005) concluded that all complaints about the teaching of Home Economics are mainly that of shortage of teachers, equipment and payment of allowance of practical lessons (for science teachers only). There is also the problem of inadequate examination assessment.

In order to overcome the problem of lack of finance, Halidu (2005) recommended that the UBE should look into the affairs of all the primary schools and be more seriously involved in the funding of Home Economics.

Statement of the Problem

UBE programme is funded by the states and local government with support from the Federal Government through its intervention fund (UBE Commission 2007). The Federal Government, as provided by the UBE Act 2004 has set aside 2% of its Consolidated Revenue Fund (CRF) to support states in the implementation of the UBE programme. This 2% of the CRF amount to ₦24.300 billion in 2005, ₦ 30.480 billion in 2006. In the 2007 budget it will be ₦35 billion (UBE Commission 2007). The states among other things are expected to provide matching grants to Federal Government intervention funds.

If all this money is invested for the UBE, then proper attention should be paid to the implementation of the new curriculum especially in the new areas of emphasis (Home Economics is one of the ten new areas) so that the money will not be wasted. There is therefore the need to examine the problems and prospects of Home Economics as introduced by the UBE in primary schools.

Research Questions

This research work sought answers to the following questions

- i. Are there enough teachers for Home Economic in the UBE programme?
- ii. Are there enough facilities for teaching of Home Economics in the UBE programme?
- iii. Are there motivational devices for effective teaching of Home Economics in the UBE programme?

Significance of the Study

This study is significant in the sense that it will shed more light on the problems and prospects of Home-Economics as introduced by the UBE in primary schools in Ondo State. It is hoped that the result of this

study will be an asset to headmaster/headmistresses and other stakeholders.

Scope of the Study

The scope of the study is Ondo State. One hundred and twenty teachers from ten primary schools in Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo local government area of Ondo State were used for the study.

Research Design and Methodology

A descriptive research and survey design was used.

Sample Selection

For the purpose of this study ten primary schools were randomly selected from the seventy-six (76) primary schools in Ile-Oluji/Okeigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. The schools were selected as follows: 3 from Ile-Oluji, 2 from Bamikemo, 3 from Okeigbo, 1 each from Awaye and Kajola to ensure representation of all the towns in the Local Government Area.

Research Instrument

A structured questionnaire containing thirty (30) items was used to collect data. The questionnaire was validated by three experts. The questionnaire was administered to twelve (12) teachers in each of the ten (10) schools. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts and percentages.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Information About The School

1	Types of school	Public 100%	Private 0%
2	Sex of teachers	Female 80%	Male 20%

From table 1 above, all schools selected were public schools. There were more female (80%) than male teachers (20%) in the schools.

Table 2: Availability of Home Economics Teachers in UBE Programme

	Yes	%	No	%
Are there enough teachers in your schools?	20	18.9	100	83.1
Are there enough Home Economics teachers in your school?	30	25	90	75

From the above table, it can be deduced that there were not enough teachers in the schools (83.1%) and also there were not enough home economics teachers (75%). If Home Economics is to be taught effectively in UBE programme, there should be enough teachers in our primary schools. Home Economics teachers should be specifically employed so that the aims of incorporating Home Economics in the curriculum will not be defeated.

Table 3: Facilities for Effective Teaching of Home Economics UBE Programme.

	Yes	%	No	%
Do you have enough instructional materials for teaching Home Economics?	37	30.8	83	69.2
Do teachers have enough textbooks for teaching Home Economics?	21	18.3	99	82
Is there any room or laboratory for Home Economics?	0	0	120	100
Are there enough facilities and equipment in the laboratory?	0	0	120	100

Table 3 above shows that 69.2% of the respondents said that the instructional materials available in their schools for teaching Home Economics were not enough. 82% responded that there were not enough textbooks. None of the schools (0%) had any room or laboratory or equipment for Home Economics. For the teaching of Home Economics to be effective and result oriented, instructional materials, good and recent textbooks, Home Economics laboratory etc. should be available in our primary schools.

Table 4: Motivational Device For Effective Teaching of Home Economics In UBE programme

	Yes	%	No	%
Do you go for excursion/workshop/seminar in Home Economics?	0	0	120	100
Do you carry out exhibition in Home Economics?	0	0	120	100
Are teachers or pupils given lunch?	0	0	120	100

Table 4 revealed that no excursion, exhibition, workshop or seminar is organized for Home Economics teachers in primary schools. Also lunch is not given to teachers or pupils to encourage them in the teaching and learning of Home Economics.

Discussion

This study revealed some factors which may pose problems to sustenance of the UBE programme. These include non-availability of teachers especially in Home Economics. According to Kattan (2006) "teacher availability-recruitment, training and deployment are still major problems faced by many countries". Others are non-availability of well equipped library with relevant textbooks, non attendance of workshop / seminar / excursion by home economics teachers, no incentives like provision of lunch for teachers, and pupils, no instructional materials to enhance teaching and learning of home economics. Ivowi (1998) summarized the problem of supply of instructional materials in the school system as:

1. Inadequate quantities of available material either in the finished or raw form.
2. High cost of production leading to unaffordable cost of books
3. Poor distribution network owing to low performance by booksellers
4. Low capital base for marketers
5. Low income of parents who pay for the instructional material.

Theobold et al (2007) in their study of Nigeria revealed that a significant improvement in PTR could be achieved if teacher deployment was supported by political will and realistic incentive.

Conclusion

For effective and successful implementation of UBE programme, there should be regular excursion, workshops and seminars for pupils and teachers of home economics in our primary schools. Teachers should be encouraged to attend exhibition on home economics wherever it is organized. They should be involved in pre-service training. That is, have the minimum teaching qualification which is the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE). They can also avail themselves of the opportunity of In-service training (Inset) organized as part-time and sandwich programmes. All these will make teachers to be effective and efficient. They should also try to organize exhibition for themselves and their pupils.

Recommendations

For the successful implementation of Home Economics curriculum and UBE programme in primary schools in Ondo State:-

- Government should employ enough qualified teachers in our primary schools to teach Home Economics and other subjects offered at primary school level.

- Primary school heads should make a room available to serve as Home Economics laboratory. Government and PTA should furnish the room with Home-Economics equipment and facilities to enhance effective teaching and learning of the subject.
- Government should supply relevant Home Economics textbooks to schools. Regular seminars, workshops and excursions should be encouraged in home economics at primary schools to equip teachers with recent and innovative methods of teaching the subjects.
- Teachers of Home Economics should be encouraged to organize exhibitions for their pupils
- Modern instructional materials should be supplied to primary schools for the teaching of the subject.
- Government should ensure that incentives to teachers and pupils of primary schools e.g. lunch (provided by the UBE programme) is implemented (to serve as encouragement to them).
- Parents should be encouraged to supply their wards with the basic needs for their education (e.g. money, school uniforms, textbooks and notebooks etc.) and create conducive home environment for the pupils to study at home.

If all the above and others suggested by other researchers are put in place, Home Economics as a subject in UBE primary education curriculum will achieve its goals and objectives and the funds invested in the programme will not be a waste.

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